

Social Issues

Interaction and Engagement

Avatar Representation and Perception

Virtual Environment Experience

Interpersonal Relationships and Identity

Accessibility and Inclusivity

Diversity Representation

Hardware and Device Accessibility

Privacy and Security

Data Theft

Identity Theft

Anonymity

User Trust

Social Norms and Ethics

Detachment From Reality

Regulation

Equality

Norm for Ensuring Inclusivity

Mental Health and Well-Being

Mental Overload

Isolation

Disconnection From Real Life

Detachment From Reality

Cyberbullying

Addiction